

THE TASKS OF DIDACTIC GAMES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN'S PICTORIAL ACTIVITIES

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Annotation: This article is devoted to conducting various meaningful role-playing, dramatizing, didactic and game games in preschool educational institutions. Thanks to this method, an easy, cheerful atmosphere created, and good results obtained by organizing game situations in training.

Key words: training, game, educator, children, fine arts, learning.

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена проведению различных содержательных ролевых, драматизирующих, дидактических и игровых игр в дошкольных образовательных учреждениях. Благодаря этому методу создается легкая, веселая атмосфера, а хорошие результаты дает организация игровых ситуаций на тренировке.

Ключевые слова: обучение, игра, воспитатель, дети, изобразительная деятельность, обучение.

Introduction. Visual arts activities related to the tasks of other learning units. In the course of teaching, the educator relies on the knowledge gained in other activities of children. If children have an idea of the subject they want to depict, it is possible to achieve effective results in drawing, clay, and applique works. Fine arts activity connected with children's play. Play takes a huge place in the life of a child. In the preschool educational institution, there are various meaningful role-playing, staged, didactic and mobile games. Any game brings joy to the child. Therefore, if the visual activity connected with the game, it will be interesting and pleasant to children; will cause an emotional state, which will have a good effect on the quality of children's work. Good results obtained by organizing game situations at training sessions. Children move freely in such classes. In all groups, the game method is used. This method creates an easy, cheerful atmosphere. Children's interest in learning will increase and they will acquire skills and competencies in visual arts. Teaching in a playful form captures children's attention, has a good influence on their aesthetic and moral education. Drawing, plasticize, cutting and pasting linked to play through the toy. Drawing, making, cutting and gluing a toy bring joy to children of all age

groups, toy-drawing classes held several times during the year. Nevertheless, their form should be different. Meaningful role-playing games play an important role in the life of a child. Therefore, the connection of pictorial activity with the game is of great importance in the education of children. The inclusion of meaningful role-playing games in the content of teaching increases the child's interest in visual activities and the quality of his work. How works play: play gives children more pleasure than drawing pictures, dry drawing, clay modeling, cutting and gluing. Play gives color to the child's experiences. The child strives for a full and vivid expression of their play pictures. In addition, the teacher must help the child in this. Dramatizing and harmonizing games with drawing, plasticine, and cutting create a great opportunity to fulfill the task of all-round development of children. Many things for theatrical games children can make themselves: scenery or their parts, costume details, masks. In drawing, cutting and pasting, the teacher gives children the task of depicting the games they play, which awakens their keen interest in drawing activities. The combination of pictorial activity with the dramatization game starts from the middle group. In drawing, clay, cutting and labeling classes, children challenged to express characters. Children enjoy the visualization of the games they play. The content of these games is easy to represent not only in pictures, but also by cutting and pasting. In the process of didactic games, children consolidate their knowledge of the signs, color, shape, structure, size, etc. of the object, get a variety of sensory experience, and enriches their understanding of the environment. The content of visual speech can be the content of didactic games themselves. Children with interest prepare didactic material. Visual activity is associated with familiarization of children with nature, speech development, music lessons. Nature always serves as the content of fine arts. Children's drawings help to clarify and consolidate their knowledge of nature; in addition, they awaken children's aesthetic feelings about the profession, which helps to make their lives more meaningful and interesting. It is very important that drawing, plasticize and cutting activities connected with speech development. In speech development classes, children read fairy tales, stories and memorized poems. In the course of these classes, children develop imaginative imagination; they try to describe the characters of fairy tales and poems in their own way, to express their attitude to them. In this useful training of fine arts activities, during which, in addition, increases the richness of speech, it enriched with figurative expressions. Fine arts and music have a positive impact on the aesthetic and creative development of children. When preschoolers asked to describe a piece

of music, this proposal arouses their keen interest. It develops children's abilities to creative search, independent composition. It is important to harmonize the visual activity of children with works of fine art. Observing samples of fine art, children not only learn more about the work of artists, but also acquire important skills in choosing the content, color and form in the drawing, learn to see the beauty and richness of art. Thus, the combination of visual arts with other activities in preschool enriches children's lives and increases the effectiveness of educational work. Another important point is that children's labor is necessary in games, decoration of halls and group rooms, i.e. children's labor should occupy a large place in their lives. Image activity is considered to be a part of educational work with children, and image activity in preschool educational organization is a part of the whole educational work with children. Therefore, it is important that it is connected with different types of activities and types of learning. The very nature of the child's image activity allows this. In painting, clay, carving, children reflect their impressions of surrounding things, events, artworks, songs. Combining drawing, modeling, cutting and constructing with other classes and activities increases the effectiveness of educational work with children, children's interest in various activities, serves to form a variety of skills. them.

Combining all kinds of activities is an opportunity to develop children's observation, curiosity, thinking, imagination, aesthetic sense, artistic taste, as well as moral qualities, the desire to work and the ability to bring the started work to the end, to overcome difficulties. Conversations with children in fine arts classes should arouse their interest in drawing and modeling things from clay. Superficial requirements that are not related to the ongoing process extinguish children's creative emotions. Classes of fine arts activities should be conducted with lively, emotional, fairy-tale elements-surprises. It is desirable to make the learning process easy so that children do not notice it. Combining visualization activities with other activities - games, art reading and storytelling, music, etc. should be done carefully. First of all, it is necessary to ensure the interdependence of painting and clay cutting and gluing activities. This has a great impact on the aesthetic education of children. Classes of fine arts activities are closely related to the tasks of other educational units. In the course of teaching, the educator relies on the knowledge gained in the children's other activities. If children have an idea of the subject they want to depict, it is possible to achieve effective results in works on drawing, clay, applique. Fine arts activities are also connected with children's games. Play plays an important role

in the life of a child. In the preschool educational organization there are various meaningful role-playing, staged, didactic and mobile games. Any game brings joy to the child. Therefore, if the visual activity connected with the game, it will be interesting and pleasant to children; will cause an emotional state, which will have a good effect on the quality of children's work. Good results obtained by organizing game situations at training sessions. Children move freely in such classes. In all groups, the game method is used. This method creates an easy, cheerful atmosphere. Children's interest in learning will increase and they will acquire skills and competencies in visual arts. Learning in a playful way captures children's attention and has a good influence on their aesthetic and moral education. Drawing, plastiline, cutting and pasting linked to play through the toy. Drawing, making, cutting and gluing a toy brings joy to children of all age groups, several toy-drawing trainings conducted throughout the year, but their form should be different. Meaningful role-playing games play an important role in a child's life. Therefore, the connection of pictorial activity with the game is of great importance in the education of children. The inclusion of meaningful role-playing games in the content of training increases the child's interest in visual activities and the quality of his work. Play is more interesting for children than drawing pictures, dry drawing, molding plasticine, cutting and gluing.

The combination of visual arts activities with dramatization play begins in the middle group. In drawing, clay, and cutting classes, children challenged to express images. A visual representation of the games they play will delight the children. The content of these games is easy to depict not only in pictures, but also by cutting and pasting. In the process of didactic games, children consolidate their knowledge of the signs, color, shape, form, structure, size, etc. of the object; get a variety of sensory experience, their understanding of the surrounding enriched. The content of visual speech can be the content of didactic games themselves. Children with interest prepare didactic material. Visual activity is associated with familiarizing children with nature, speech development, musical training. Nature always serves as the content of fine arts. Children's drawings help to clarify and consolidate their knowledge of nature, and children have.

In conclusion, it said that building and making with the necessary materials in preschool educational organizations forms children's visual perception and helps children to master pictorial activities. At the classes on drawing nature in a large group of preschool educational institution they learn to think logically, observe, distinguish the main features, analyze the spatial characteristics of the

object, and independently choose pictorial means. All of these are necessary in the process of learning in school. Thus, the teacher should be able to make a correct diagnosis and guide the development of artistic taste and creative abilities in children, preparing them for schooling, when teaching children's visual arts activities.

References:

1. Sadykova Sh.A. Preschool pedagogy. T.: Mysl Boston 2013
2. N. Kayumova. Preschool pedagogy. T.: TDPU 2013.
3. Hasanova Sh.T. Theory and methodology of teaching visual arts activities. T.: TDPU 2019.
4. Methodology of drawing, making objects and fine arts activities. M. Sh. Nurmatova
...
<http://kutubkhona.adu.uz/kutubkhona/53rasmbuyumlaryasashpdf.pdf>
5. Nurmatova Sh., Khasanova Sh., Azimova D.E. Practical lessons in the workshop. T. 2010. Publishing house "Cholpon".
6. "Is your child ready for school?" methodological manual. T: 2001.
7. Hasanboyeva et al. Family pedagogy. T.: "Alohachi", 2007.
8. Askarali Sulaimanov Sculpture classes in preschool educational institutions T.-2015.<http://library.ziyonet.uz/ru/book/35985>.
9. Amirova G.A., Sulaimonov A.P., Dzhuraev B.R. Organization of applied learning in preschool educational institutions. T.-2014. Scientific and methodological manual.

